

A comparative study on labour induction with combined oral misoprostol and Foley catheter versus oral misoprostol alone at term gestation in a tertiary care centre

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Labour induction is the predominant obstetric intervention. Labour induction can be achieved through multiple methods, including the use of pharmacological agents (e.g., misoprostol) and the utilization of mechanical agents (e.g., the Foley catheter). This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of oral misoprostol combined with Foley's catheter compared to oral misoprostol alone for labour induction.

Material and Methods:

This prospective randomised control study was conducted in Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology in Trichy SRM Medical College, for a period of 6 months. A total of 60 primi mothers with term gestation and single live pregnancy with indications for induction like diabetes complicating pregnancy, chronic hypertension, gestational hypertension, pre eclampsia, PROM, term gestation, post dated pregnancy, IUGR was included in the study. After getting informed written consent from the patients, they were randomly allocated into two groups (Group A and Group B) consisting of 30 participants each. Group A participants received Oral misoprostol of 50 µg, every 4 hours for a maximum of 5 doses. Group B participants received intracervical 22 French Foley catheter for a maximum period of 12 hrs followed by oral misoprostol of 50 µg every 4 hours for a maximum of 5 doses. Foley balloon was inflated with 60 mL of normal saline. The external end of the catheter was taped to the inner side of the thigh with gentle traction. A semi-structured validated questionnaire was used to collect the demographic details, presenting complaints, obstetric history, menstrual history, personal history, and any surgical and medical history. Vitals were recorded and a complete physical and systemic examination, per abdominal and per vaginal examination was done to all the study participants. Bishop's score was assessed and all the data were documented. Data analysis was done using SPSS and continuous variables and categorical variables were interpreted using frequencies (mean±SD) and proportions (%).

Results:

The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group. There was no significant difference in the mean maternal age ($p = 0.520$) or BMI ($p = 0.728$) between the groups. The comparison of labour progression parameters demonstrated that the mean number of misoprostol doses required did not differ significantly between the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group ($p = 0.453$). The total induction-to-delivery interval and induction to active labour duration was significantly shorter in the Misoprostol only group compared to the Foley + Misoprostol group. The no. of oxytocin drops/min is significantly lower in Foley+Miso group. Non-progression of labour and non-reassuring fetal heart rate pattern were observed sporadically in either group. The low APGAR score at birth show statistically significant differences between the two study groups.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, induction with Misoprostol alone has shorter induction to delivery interval and the combination treatment for labour induction has a better fetal outcome and reduced number of doses of Misoprostol, as well as reduced complication rates.

Keywords: Foley Catheter, oral misoprostol, labour induction

Introduction

Labour induction is a commonly employed obstetric procedure aimed to provoke uterine contractions prior to the natural commencement of labour when the continuation of pregnancy threatens mother or fetal health. The worldwide incidence of labour induction has markedly risen owing to enhancements in obstetric care, the development of clinical guidelines advocating for prompt delivery to prevent complications. In developed countries, up to 25% of term deliveries necessitate labour induction, whereas this figure is roughly 9.6% in developing countries. [1,2]

Labour induction is a commonly employed technique in the management of high-risk pregnancies. Indications for induction encompass post-term pregnancy, premature rupture of membranes (PROM), hypertensive disorders such as pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, gestational diabetes, pre gestational diabetes, multiple gestations, with post-term pregnancy being a prevalent indication.[3]

Induction techniques are often classified into mechanical and pharmacological ways. Mechanical techniques, such as transcervical Foley catheter insertion, apply direct pressure on the cervix, facilitating the release of endogenous prostaglandins and cervical ripening. Pharmacological medications, especially misoprostol, a synthetic analogue of prostaglandin E1, are extensively utilized to efface and dilate the cervix, thereby inducing uterine contractions. Although both strategies are efficacious, each possesses distinct advantages and limits. [4,5]

Mechanical approaches have been associated to a reduced risk of uterine hyper-stimulation, while pharmaceutical treatments may induce labour more rapidly but carry an increased risk of tachy-systole and utero-placental insufficiency.[6] A meta-analysis by Chen W et al indicated that vaginal misoprostol was the most efficacious technique for cervical ripening to facilitate vaginal birth within 24 hours, with the highest occurrence of uterine hyper-stimulation accompanied by fetal heart rate (FHR) alterations. The exclusive use of a Foley catheter was linked to the minimal incidence of uterine hyper-stimulation with concomitant fetal heart rate alterations.[7]

Recent studies suggest that the combination of mechanical and pharmacological approaches for cervical ripening in women with an unfavourable cervix may improve efficacy while reducing individual risks. A combined technique utilizing a Foley catheter with misoprostol has been presented, indicating that both ripening drugs function separately rather than

synergistically. Intra-vaginal misoprostol has been documented as more efficacious in enhancing cervical length and consistency scores, however the trans-cervical Foley catheter is superior in augmenting the cervical os dilation score during pre-induction cervical ripening.[8,9]

Due to the scarcity of research comparing the efficacy of combination methods vs single methods, this study was undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of Foley's catheter combined with oral misoprostol against oral misoprostol alone in labour induction.

Aim & Objective

- To compare the efficacy of labour induction with combined Foley Catheter and oral misoprostol versus oral misoprostol alone at term gestation.

Material and Methods

- Study design
 - A Prospective randomised controlled trail study
- Study area
 - Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SRM medical college, Trichy
- Study duration
 - Six months
- Study population
 - All primi mothers with single live pregnancy with cephalic presentation at ≥ 37 weeks gestation with valid indication for induction.
- Inclusion criteria
 - Primi mothers with single live pregnancy with cephalic presentation at ≥ 37 weeks gestation with valid indication for induction.
 - Patients with age between 20-30 yrs
 - Bishop's score < 4
 - Foley catheter in situ for more than 6hrs for group B.
- Exclusion criteria
 - History of cessarean delivery or other uterine surgery
 - Chorioamnionitis
 - Any contraindication to the use of misoprostol and /or vaginal delivery
 - Participants not willing to give consent

- Indication for induction
 - Gestational diabetes mellitus
 - Overt diabetes mellitus
 - Gestational hypertension
 - Chronic hypertension
 - Pre-eclampsia
 - Oligohydramnios
 - IUGR
 - PROM
 - Post-dated pregnancy
- Sampling technique
 - Consecutive sampling

- Sample size: 60

- Data collection

The present study was conducted in Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology in SRM College, Trichy for a period of 6 months. This study was conducted among 60 primi mothers with term gestation and single live pregnancy. After getting informed written consent from the patients, they were randomly allocated into two groups (Group A and Group B) consisting of 30 participants each.

- Group A participants received Oral misoprostol of 50µg, every 4 hours for a maximum of 5 doses
- Group B participants received intra-cervical 22 French Foley catheter for a maximum period of 12 hrs. followed by oral misoprostol of 50 µg every 4 hours for a maximum of 5 doses. Foley balloon was inflated with 60 mL of normal saline. The external end of the catheter was taped to the inner side of the thigh with gentle traction.

A semi-structured validated questionnaire was used to collect the demographic details, presenting complaints, obstetric history, menstrual history, personal history, and any surgical and medical history. Vitals were recorded and a complete physical and systemic examination was done to all the study participants. Per abdomen examination was performed to ascertain period of gestation, lie, presentation, and fetal heart rate. Per-vaginal examination was done and Bishop's score was assessed and all the data were documented.

All the collected data was entered in Microsoft excel 2019 and analysed using software SPSS (Statistical Package of Social Sciences) version 21. Continuous variables and categorical variables were interpreted using frequencies (mean \pm SD) and proportions (%). Chi square test and T -test was used to compare the variables and P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

- **Outcome measured**

Group A	Group B
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No. of doses of Tab. Misoprostol ● Interval between each doses ● Induction to start of active labour ● Start of oxytocin ● Duration of oxytocin ● Oxytocin to delivery interval ● Induction to delivery interval ● Mode of delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Duration of Foley catheter ● No. of doses of Tab. Misoprostol ● Interval between each doses ● Induction to start of active labour ● Start of oxytocin ● Duration of oxytocin ● Oxytocin to delivery interval ● Induction to delivery interval ● Mode of delivery

- **Ethical issues**

- Participants were informed about the study and informed consent was obtained
- This study was presented to Institutional Ethical Committee of Trichy SRM Medical College and hospital, Trichy.

Results

This study was conducted among 60 primi mothers with single live pregnancy at term gestation.

Table 1: Baseline data

VARIABLES	Foley+Misoprostol group	Misoprostol group	P value
Age in years	24.13+/-2.54	23.63+/-3.37	0.520
Comorbidities			
GDM	9, (30%)	5, 16.7	0.621
GHTN	5, (16.7%)	4, 13.4	
Bronchial asthma	1, (3.3%)	2, 6.7	
Hypothyroidism	3, (10%)	6, 20	
Nil	12, (40%)	13, 43.3	
BMI	27.3+/-4.04	27.37+/-5.05	0.728
Indication for induction			
GHTN or	5,(16.6%)	4, 13.3	0.267
Preeclampsia	9, (30%)	5, 16.6	
GDM	2, (6.6%)	1, 3.3	
IUGR	1, (3.3%)	0	
Oligohydraminos	0	6, 20	
PROM	13, (43.3%)	14, 46.6	
Term			
Bishop score			
2	19, (63.3%)	18, 60	0.963
3	11, (36.7%)	12, 40	

The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group. There was no significant difference in the mean maternal age ($p = 0.520$) or BMI ($p = 0.728$) between the groups. The distribution of associated comorbidities, including gestational diabetes mellitus, gestational hypertension, bronchial asthma, and hypothyroidism, did not show statistically significant variation ($p = 0.621$). Likewise, the indications for induction of labour were similar across groups ($p = 0.267$). The pre-induction Bishop scores demonstrated no significant difference ($p = 0.963$),

Table 2: Induction details

VARIABLES	Foley+Misoprostol group	Misoprostol group	P value
No. of Misoprostol dose	2.66+/-1.42	2.93+/-1.31	0.453
No. of oxytocin drops/min	16+/-1.1	24.2+/-1.63	<0.001
Duration of oxytocin in mins	69.13+/-53.8	96.08+/-72.50	0.159
Oxytocin to delivery in mins	71.75+/-57.73	96.09+/-72.5	0.214
Induction to active labour hours	16.7+/-2.31	8.11+/-1.23	<0.001
Induction to delivery in hours	20.25+/-8.39	14.93+/-6.59	0.008

The comparison of labour progression parameters demonstrated that the mean number of misoprostol doses required did not differ significantly between the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group ($p = 0.453$). Similarly, the duration of oxytocin administration ($p = 0.159$) and the interval from initiation of oxytocin to delivery ($p = 0.214$) were comparable between the two study groups, indicating no statistically significant variation in augmentation requirements. The total induction-to-delivery interval and induction to active labour duration was significantly shorter in the Misoprostol only group compared to the Foley + Misoprostol group. The no. of oxytocin drops/min is significantly lower in Foley+Miso group

Figure 1: Induction to delivery**Table 3: Mode of delivery**

VARIABLES	Foley+Misoprostol group	Misoprostol group	P value
Mode of delivery			
NVD	14, (46.7%)	14, 46.7	0.913
NVD with forceps or vacuum assistance	5, (16.6 %)	6, 20	
LSCS	11, (36.7%)	10, 33.3	

The mode of delivery comparison shows there is no significant difference in mode of delivery between two groups.

Figure 2: Mode of delivery

Figure 3: Indication for LSCS

The distribution of indications for cesarean section was comparable between the two groups. Persistent fetal tachycardia was the most frequent indication in both the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group (3 cases each). Failed induction accounted for 4 cases in the Foley + Misoprostol group and 3 cases in the Misoprostol-only group. Non-progression of labour and non-reassuring fetal heart rate pattern were observed sporadically in either group. Grade 2/3 meconium-stained liquor and fetal bradycardia occurred with equal frequency in both arms. There is no significance in the cesarean indications.

Table 4: Low APGAR score, Need of NICU and MSL in babies

Variables	Foley+Misoprosto l group	Misoprostol group	P value
NICU admission	4, 13.3	6, 20	0.688
MSL	3, 10	6, 20	0.281
Low APGAR score	0, 0	5, 16.67	0.020

Neonatal outcomes showed no statistically significant differences between the two study groups. The proportion of neonates requiring NICU admission was similar in the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group (13.3% vs. 20%, $p = 0.688$). Also meconium-stained liquor did not differ significantly between the groups. The low APGAR score at birth show statistically significant differences between the two study groups

Discussion

The present study aimed to evaluate and compare the efficacy and safety of two labour induction methods: the combination of misoprostol and Foley catheter versus oral misoprostol alone in women. The oral misoprostol alone resulted in a significantly shorter induction-delivery time interval compared to combination of the Foley catheter and misoprostol.

Our study report is comparable to research by Beyrami et al.[10], which indicated that the interval from the initiation of intervention to delivery exhibited a significant decrease of roughly 8 hours in the combination group compared to oral misoprostol alone. The study indicated that the reduced occurrence of tachysystole in the combined group implies possible safety benefits concerning the frequency of maternal problems. Anjali et al.[11] conducted another study indicating that the mean induction-to-active-labour interval is significantly diminished with the combined application of a Foley catheter and oral misoprostol ($P=.001$) compared to the use of oral misoprostol alone. Likewise, the mean interval from induction to full dilatation was significantly decreased ($P=.001$) by the combination, paralleling our study findings.

A study conducted by Graham et al.[12] revealed that the mean duration of the induction-to-onset-of-active-labour interval was significantly shorter (by 151 minutes) in the combination group, although the mean induction-to-full-dilatation time was comparable which is also comparable to our study report. Balamurugan et al.[13] conducted a study indicating that the mean induction-to-active-labour period was substantially shorter in the combination group compared to the oral misoprostol group (9 vs. 18 hours; $P = .002$) which is in consistent with present study.

Our study report stated that neonatal outcomes showed no statistically significant differences between the two study groups. The proportion of neonates requiring NICU admission was similar in the Foley + Misoprostol group and the Misoprostol-only group (13.3% vs. 20%, $p = 0.688$). Also meconium-stained liquor did not differ significantly between the groups. This was similar to a study conducted by Graham et al and Adhikari et al[14] stated that there is no significant difference was found in the incidence of maternal or neonatal complications. According to a meta-analysis conducted by McMaster et al.,[15] transcervical catheters did not correlate with increased risks of maternal or fetal infection.

Conclusion

The study determined that the combined regimen of Foley catheter and oral misoprostol was efficacious, simple to use, and significantly reduced labour duration, warranting its consideration for normal practice. The combination of Foley's catheter induction and misoprostol exhibited a synergistic effect, leading to a reduced duration to transition to the active phase, a shorter induction-to-delivery interval, and an increased likelihood of vaginal delivery compared to the administration of oral misoprostol alone.

Limitations

- The larger sample size might be considered for generalising results.

Conflict of interest

- Nil

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